

Role of Print Media in China-Pakistan Economic Corridor as Stakeholder

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Abstract—Media has become an integral part of society as it influences the society by several ways. The basic functions of the media are to inform, educate and entertain the masses. In the modern world media not only inform, educate and entertain the societies but the extended roles of the media have many other dimensions as well. Media has become the mirror of the society, so it is a duty of the media managers to show the actual face of the society via media. Media is creating sensation around this region by putting its active role on the audience through highlighting the news stories about china-pakistan economic corridor (CPEC) and also representing information of stakeholders in mass media in their own subjective and their own situation. CPEC being one of the most important economic projects in the region will be the game changer for Pakistan and due to the investments and interest of regional powers CPEC is stuck down into the neck of many countries. It is fact that once this project is completed it will boost the Pakistan's economy and it will definitely go upwards. There are enormous studies on CPEC but no study has focused on the media representation as stakeholder. This study explored the new dimensions of CPEC and the role of media representing as stakeholders. The news stories are very informative and played a very effective role on citizens of Pakistan in order to share a concrete and prompt information regarding CPEC. Dawn (English) and Jang (Urdu) are the leading newspaper in Pakistan and considered as opinion maker in the country. These newspapers have played a vital role in changing mind frame of public and even policy makers. These newspapers are not the authority to make policy but it makes ground on which policies are made. The media is playing its role effectively in eliminating information gap through building the positive image in the minds of the stakeholders. The media is publishing positive image news more so as to build a linkage and bridge between the stakeholders. The positive statements of the authorities are published more highlighting the fact that the most of the stakeholders are motivated to have the maximum.

Keywords— China, Pakistan, Economic, Corridor, Media, Balochistan

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I. INTRODUCTION

Pakistan needs a high cooperation from its allies in especially in Southern Asian region in order to have its deterrence and sovereignty. This explored the need of something special to meet the needs of the country that may click its social, economic and development programs for its growth. CPEC is the brick of such milestone that will bring it closer to achieve its objective. Being the invader to the new horizons, Pakistan has got a great attention through the world especially in stakeholders of CPEC [1]. This has developed a gap between these stakeholders due to the importance and vitality of the corridor. This gap is increasing due to the conflicts in the nation affecting the stability, economy and most importantly, peace of the country. The main idea of the journalism is also in this context as the importance of economic growth cannot be denied [2]. Under this concept, the news stories are presented in such a brilliant manner that highlights the economic position of the country as well as about the other stakeholders' interests. Same is the case with CPEC and significantly, the role of media is an integral part within the development of this project [3].

Now a day, media is also influencing the policy making decisions. Role of the media in this regard, is not new as it has been studied already in early 1940's when the Paul Lazarsfeld, conducted a land mark study about the role of the media in the US Presidential elections. Paul Lazarsfeld's study paved a way towards the role of media in opinion making during US presidential elections [4,5].

In choosing and displaying news, editors, newsroom staff, and broadcasters play an important part in shaping political reality. Readers learn not only about a given issue, but how importance to attach to that issue from the amount of information in a news story and its position the mass media may well determine the important issues- that is, the media may set the 'agenda' of the campaign [6,7].

II. METHODOLOGY

The objective of the study isto analyze how news stories cover the CPEC in Pakistan print media and how print media represents different stakeholders. For the purpose, researchers texture the study in the Qualitative and / or Quantitative research methods. In this research study "Quantitative method" is used; in which Content Analysis technique is organized.

A. Quantitative Method

Quantitative research requires that the variables under consideration be measured. This form of research is concerned with how often a variable is presented and generally uses

numbers to communicate this amount. Quantitative research has certain advantages. The use of numbers allows greater precision in reporting results. In this research method, the procedure applies to evaluate the result in the numeric values. It is not as same qualitative method. The focal distinguish among qualitative and quantitative is generalization of result. Both research methods have the certain style to carry out the study. Content Analysis is a method to formulate the tone, nature, theme, and significance of the study. The aim to determine the news stories of Daily Dawn (English) and Daily Jang (Urdu). A Content Analysis technique has used [8,9].

B. Content Analysis

Content Analysis is a technique for examining the content or information and symbols contained in written documents or other communication media (e.g, photographs, movies, song lyrics, advertisements). To conduct a content analysis, we identify a body of materials to analyze e.g, school textbooks, television programs, newspapers articles and then create a system of recording specific aspects of this content [10,11]. In a systematic procedure of content analysis, research looks closely the matter on subject. This technique allows the study to analyze the study from each and every aspect. The deep observation to evaluate each and every part of subject in this study, researcher determines news stories of the Daily Dawn and Daily Jang newspapers. In a study conducted by Jam Macnamara, articulates the usage and benefits of content analysis. Mass media research is now having wide and extended range of data. To analyze the every bit of news story, script, document, editorial, column, movies and sounds; content analysis is a tool which provides wide range to study [12].

The current study dissected the part of print media in building the significance of CPEC in Pakistan through its noticeable Urdu & English newspapers.

C. Data Collection

The researcher collected the sample consisted of news stories of four months in Daily Dawn (English) and Daily Jang (Urdu) newspapers with timeframe from November 2015 to February 2016. The news stories published in both selected newspapers are collected.

D. Sample

This study investigates the news stories regarding coverage of CPEC and presentation of its stakeholders published by Pakistan two prominent newspapers Dawn (English) and Jang (Urdu). The background of news collection within this time period is due to that the CPEC has been launched in this period and the development of CPEC is under progress in this phase of time. In this period, different statements of stakeholders' authorities had been published. Therefore the researcher selected this time period because this time period seemed to be very critical as far as CPEC progress and launch is concerned. This study emphasizes on the news stories published in newspapers for CPEC progress and its launch. The data set consisted of 200 news stories which were published in selected newspapers, in which Dawn (English) contributed with 120 news and Jang (Urdu) contributed with 80 news stories in the four months of timeframe. To get the representative sample all

the news stories depicting the economic, social, and cultural development of Pakistan nation due to CPEC as well as the implementation strategies, their tactics, the pros and cons of CPEC, statements of the authorities of CPEC stakeholders are selected for the analysis [13,14,15].

III. RESULTS

The result shows that the news coverage varied before and after the inauguration of CPEC. This is due to the fact that the journalism gave coverage to the launch of CPEC. It was under publishing process while it was in planning process but when it is launched, the media coverage started doing a campaign in the favor of this project as shown in Table-1.

TABLE I. NEWS CONTENTS BEFORE & AFTER CPEC LAUNCH

Newspaper	Before CPEC Launch	After CPEC Launch	Total
Dawn	50	70	120
Jang	35	45	80
Total	85	115	200

This will envision the people so as they would know that the project is in the favor of the Pakistani nation. These reports were highlighting the importance of the corridor on the Southern Asian region. Furthermore, these reports were used to envision the investments that would be forecasted to dump in Pakistan economy. These reports highlight the distinction Pakistan and China will have over other nations through this corridor. Undoubtedly, there are news stories published before the launch of CPEC, they are found to be the part of media campaign of Pakistan govt. So as they should be delivering their message to the nation as well as other stakeholders that this project is not going to be sabotaged under the political and terrorism concern Pakistan was facing. The data consists of 200 news stories in which Dawn contributes more (with 120 news) than Jang (with 80 news). It is quite clear through the table that the number of news stories become greater after the launch of CPEC. Moreover, it is quite clear that the news stories after the launch are more informative and descriptive in nature as compared to the before launch stories because before were the part of media campaign as shown in Figure-1.

Figure 1. News Contents before and after CPEC launch

The result of research presents whether CPEC bridges different nations and regions together and through this linkage results in the growth and development in all the stakeholders involved with this project especially Pakistan and China. The development category is divided into three sub-categories: economic, social and cultural as shown in Table-2.

TABLE II. ROLE OF NEWSPAPERS IN DEVELOPMENT OF CPEC

Newspaper	Economic Development	Social Development	Cultural Development	Total
Dawn	45	35	40	120
Jang	35	25	20	80
Total	80	60	60	200

In the news stories of selected newspapers, the Dawn publishes 45 news stories relating to economic development (37.5 %), 35 stories were published on social development (29 %) and 40 news were published relative to the cultural development (34 %). In contrast, Jang comprised 35 news stories in favor of economic development (43.75 %), 25 were published on social development (31%) and 20 news stories were depicting cultural development (25%) as shown in Figure-2.

Figure 2. Role of Newspapers in Development of CPEC

The results are depicting that the focus of Jang is more on economic development as compare to the Dawn, whereas Dawn is focusing more on cultural development of the society of the stakeholders than Jang. Both the newspapers are emphasizing on the development but the difference is that Jang is emphasizing on the economic aspect whereas Dawn is emphasizing on the cultural development of the society. This reveals that media campaign is working on all sub-categories indicate that the informational gap which is arising in the stakeholders could be eliminated in a positive manner. This of the development of CPEC. The results of last question informational gap is being created due to the fact that Pakistan and China are the major stakeholders of this project and are strategic partners too. This sense stresses the other stakeholders about their interests and they feel themselves at the lower levels of benefits as compared to Pakistan and China are concerned. These statements have been categorized in two

dimensions: positive and negative. Positive statements are those given in the favor of project whereas negative statements have the adverse thought for the project. The daily Dawn has published 91 news stories comprising the positive statements of the stakeholders' authorities which is 76 % whereas the news comprising the negative statements are 29 making 24 % (Table-3).

TABLE III. POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE STATEMENTS OF NEWS

Newspaper	Positive Statements	Negative Statements	Total
Dawn	91	29	120
Jang	54	26	80
Total	145	55	200

This shows that the daily Dawn is emphasizing the positive image of the stakeholders regarding CPEC. On the other hand, the news published in the daily Jang containing the positive statements of stakeholders authorities are 54 (67.5 %) whereas the news containing negative statements are 26 (32.5 %). The results indicate both the newspapers are highlighting the positive dimensions of the authorities' statements and trying to eliminate the informational gap as much as possible as shown in Figure-3.

Figure 3. News contents containing Positive and Negative Statements

IV. DISCUSSIONS

The objective of this study is to identify the extent of news stories which were published in two prominent newspapers daily Dawn (English) and daily Jang (Urdu) of Pakistan covering CPEC and how print media represents its stakeholders these news stories also act as media campaign for CPEC. This is the only study that is analyzing the role of print media in creating an influence in the minds of audience as well as in eliminating the informational gap between CPEC stakeholders by highlighting the importance and socio economic development projects. Moreover, the role of print media in analyzing the prominent newspapers contents regarding CPEC information to the audience and representation of its stakeholders.

The results indicate the media campaign was carried on before the launch of the CPEC in order to publicize and to create awareness in the minds of audience which is lesser than after the launch depicting that the media is playing its important role in implementation stage as well. After launching

of the CPEC the media campaign highlights that the media is providing information to the stakeholders in the abundant manner so as they should know each and every aspect of the project and can get the maximum benefit.

It is evident that the media is playing its role in the development of the Southern Asian Region economically, socially and culturally. The media is highlighting these three kinds of developments occurring in the stakeholders due to involvement in this project as different nations are working in it. This will lower down the tensions across the borders and will build a bridge for multilateral trade and cultural diffusion. The media campaign is very effective in determining the mind frame of the audience as according to cultivation theory, the media is playing an active role and audience is on passive mode. Overall through this project, there will be prosperity among the stakeholders and they will be found in good position financially, morally, and culturally. This all is due to effective and positive role of mass media in Pakistan.

The findings indicate the frequency of positive and negative statements regarding CPEC and its stakeholders in the coverage of the newspapers. The media is playing its role effectively in eliminating information gap through building the positive image in the minds of the stakeholders. The print media is publishing positive image news more so as to build a linkage and bridge the gap between stakeholders. The positive statements of the authorities are published more highlighting the fact that the most of the stakeholders are motivated to have the maximum benefits from these projects.

CONCLUSIONS

The overall results of the study show that the media campaign of CPEC in Pakistan by the Pakistan two prominent newspapers Dawn and Jang tilt towards the importance of CPEC among their stakeholders and to play a dominant role in eliminating the informational gap between them in which both the newspapers are playing their role in building a positive image among the stakeholders. The news stories published before and after the inauguration of CPEC exhibit the complete range of media campaign starting from the planning to the effective implementation.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. Ijaz, F. Shamailla, and G. Saima, 2016. "China-Pakistan Economic Corridor: News Discourse Analysis of Indian Print Media," *J. Pol. Stud.*, vol.23(1), pp. 233-252, 2016.
- [2] W. L. Neuman, *Content Analysis*. Noida: Pearson Handbook Mill Valley, CA: University Science, 2015.
- [3] J. Macnamara, "Media content analysis: Its uses; benefits and best practice methodology," *Asia. Pac. Pub. Rela. J.*, vol. 1, pp. 34, 2005.
- [4] D. Chong, and J. Druckman, "A Theory of Framing and Opinion Formation in Competitive Elite Environments," *J. Com.*, vol. 1, pp. 99-118, 2007.
- [5] E. Katz, and P.F. Lazarsfeld, "Personal Influence, the Part Played by People in the Flow of Mass Communications,". New Brunswick: Transaction Publishers, 2009

- [6] M. Maxwell, *The Agenda Setting Function of Mass media*, 176, 1972.
- [7] C.K. Daly, "India unsettled by proposed China Pakistan Economic Corridor through Kashmir", *The. Jam. Foun.*, vol. 14(5), pp. 4-6. 2014.
- [8] V. T. Dijk, "Discourse analysis: Its development and application to the structure of news", *J. Comm.*, vol.3(2), pp. 20-43, 1983.
- [9] V.H. Pant, "The Pakistan thorn in China-India-U.S. relations", *The. Wash. Quart.*, vol. 1(35), pp. 83-95, 2012.
- [10] . A.T. Yousaf, "Is Gwadar Port an economic haven for Balochistan and Pakistan? (Master's thesis)", Retrieved from <https://eh1.u.se>, 2012.
- [12] Z. Pan, and G. M. Kosicki, "Framing analysis: An approach to news Discourse", *Poli. Comm.*, vol. 10, pp. 53-75, 1993.
- [13] Gilgit-Baltistan pols to camouflage Pak's forcible occupation, India says. (2015, June 3). *Times of India*. Retrieved from <http://timesofindia.com>.
- [14] India expresses concerns over China Pakistan Economic Corridor. (2014, April 14). *The Economic Times*. Retrieved from <http://articles.indiatimes.com>.
- [15] Emphasis on Gwadar-Kashgar Corridor. (2015, April 21). *The Hindu*. Retrieved from <tps://thehindu.com>.